
Multiscale analysis for woven composite with incomplete periodicity

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Introduction

□ 3D woven CFRP

- Three-dimensionally oriented fiber bundles.
- Higher impact resistance and rigidity in the thickness direction.

□ Challenges

- Many factors affect material properties.

Type of fiber or resin, fiber orientation
+
Complex structures and crimp of fiber

Multiscale analysis based on in-plane periodicity of woven structure

The model is separated into two scale.

- RUC : Representative Unit Cell = microscopic scale
 - Structural scale treated as a homogeneous material = macroscopic scale
- } Analyze in relation

Conventional multiscale analysis

Microscopic displacement

$$u_i(y_1, y_2, y_3) = \tilde{E}_{ij}y_j + \tilde{K}_{ij}y_jy_3 + u_i^\#(y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

\tilde{E}_{ij} : Macroscopic strain

\tilde{K}_{ij} : Macroscopic curvature

Assumption : **Strict in-plane periodicity** exists between adjacent RUC.

The shape of one surface and its opposite surface must match and have the same microscopic deformation.

$$u_i^\#(-a, y_2, y_3) = u_i^\#(+a, y_2, y_3)$$

□ Periodic boundary condition

$$\begin{aligned}u_1(a, y_2, y_3) - u_1(-a, y_2, y_3) &= 2aE_{11} + 2ay_3K_{11} \\u_2(a, y_2, y_3) - u_2(-a, y_2, y_3) &= 2aE_{12} + 2ay_3K_{12} \\u_3(a, y_2, y_3) - u_3(-a, y_2, y_3) &= -2ay_2K_{12}\end{aligned}$$

□ Key-DOF method^[1]

- Add imaginary nodes (with six degrees of freedom) at an arbitrary location.
- Enforce macroscopic strain to the key degree of freedom.

[1]: S. Li, N. Warror, Z. Zou, F. Almaskari: A unit cell for FE analysis of materials with the microstructure of a staggered pattern, Composites: Part A, Vol. 42 (2011), pp. 801-811.

Introduction

Strict periodicity does not exist in actual materials.

3D woven composite

Microscopic defects such as tow waviness and tow distortion occur in fiber bundles.

Apply the conventional periodic boundary condition

- ✓ The shape of RUC must be **idealized** to impose periodic boundary conditions.
 - It is impossible to connect the corresponding nodes on fiber bundles (or resin) surface each other.
- ✓ The effect of microscopic defects **must be ignored**.

Objective

Propose a multiscale analysis method for RUC with **incomplete periodicity** due to microscopic defects.

Tow waviness obtained by X-ray CT images^[2]

A model which does not have strict periodicity.

[2]: Hiroyuki Hashimoto, Microstructural Modeling of Three-Dimensional Woven Composite Materials and Validation through Damage Observation, Master's thesis, Tokyo University of Science, 2018.

Multiscale analysis considering microscopic defects

□ Basic concept

1. Assume an ideal arrangement (**nominal location**) which has strict periodicity.
2. Consider the **actual location** to be slightly deviated from the nominal location due to microscopic defects.
3. Associate actual locations with nominal locations.
4. Impose periodic boundary conditions on the **nominal location** using Key-DOF method.

□ Advantage

- Easy implementation to the commercial FE software.

□ Note

- Applicable only when microscopic defects are small.

Formulation

Assume that a point P in the nominal model (position vector y_i) moves to a point P^1 (position vector y_i^1) in the actual model due to microscopic defects \hat{u}_i :

$$y_i^1 = y_i + \hat{u}_i \cdots (1)$$

Microscopic displacement at point P^1 in the actual model :

$$u_i(y_i^1) = \tilde{E}_{ij}y_j + \tilde{K}_{ij}y_jy_3 + u_i^1(y_i) \cdots (2)$$

Macroscopic strain at point P^1 :

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{E}_{ij}^{real} &= \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_{Y^1} \varepsilon_{ij} dY^1 = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \varepsilon_{ij} \det|J| dY \\ &= \tilde{E}_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \tilde{E}_{ik} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \tilde{E}_{jk} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_i} dY \cdots (3) \end{aligned}$$

(Terms related to macroscopic curvature are omitted. $|Y^1|$ denotes the volume.)

Unlike \tilde{E}_{ij} enforced in the nominal model, \tilde{E}_{ij}^{real} includes additional correction terms.

The macroscopic strain at point P^1 can be written by applying a transformation matrix $[X]$ to the macroscopic strain enforced at point P :

$$\tilde{E}_{real} = [X] \tilde{E} \cdots (4)$$

※ $[X]$ corresponds to the coefficient matrix appearing in equation (3).

Formulation

Similarly, for the resultant force

$$\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{real} = [Y] \tilde{\mathbf{N}} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{real} = [X] \tilde{\mathbf{E}} \quad \dots (4)$$

From the energy relation,

$$\frac{1}{2} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{real}^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{real} = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}} \quad \dots (6)$$

Substituting equation (4)

$$\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{real} = [X]^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}} \quad \dots (7)$$

From the stress-strain relationship,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{N}} = [C_{key}] \tilde{\mathbf{E}} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_{real} = [C_{real}] \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{real} \quad \dots (9)$$

Calculated by the Key-DOF method

Combining equations (4), (7), (8) and (9), the stiffness matrix of the actual model is

$$[C_{real}] = [X]^T [C_{key}] [X] \quad \dots (10)$$

From the **stiffness matrix** $[C_{key}]$ (calculated by Key-DOF method) and the **transformation matrix** $[X]$ (calculated by microscopic defects \hat{u}_i), the stiffness matrix of the actual model can be obtained.

Challenges for application to 3D woven CFRP model

woven CFRP mesh

Conventional modeling approach

- Idealize the complex woven structure.
- Generate meshes so that the resin conforms along the interfaces of the fiber bundles.

Considering microscopic defects

- The interface geometry becomes even more complex.
- Very difficult to generate a conforming resin mesh.

Mesh-separated analysis method^[3]

- Separately mesh the fiber bundles and the resin.
- Mesh separation is straightforward and takes less time.

Fiber bundles mesh

Resin mesh

Mesh-separated analysis method^[3]

Separately mesh the fiber bundles and the resins.

Remove the void elements

- **Void elements** (Completely overlapped by fiber bundles. removed in advance.)
- **Cut elements** (Partially overlapped by fiber bundles.)
- **Normal elements** (Not overlapped by fiber bundles at all.)

Resin elements used in analysis ←

Three types of resin elements.

Cut elements

- The interface between fiber bundles and resins **exists in cut elements**.
- The interface is represented based on the relationship between the cohesive traction and the relative displacement. \Rightarrow **Cohesive zone model**^[4]

□ Procedure

1. The stiffness of fiber bundles : K^L , and the stiffness of resins : K^G are calculated conventionally.
2. The interface stiffness : K_c is calculated using ABAQUS user subroutine (UEL).
3. They are merged into the global stiffness equation : $(K^L + K^G + K_c)\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}$.

Analysis model

A simple model with a single fiber bundle embedded in resin.

Nodes: 41,613, Elements: 11,240
 Fiber bundles : tetra element (C3D4), Resin: hexa element (C3D8)
 y_1 7.2 mm \times y_2 3.6 mm \times y_3 1.1 mm

□ Microscopic defects (only to a fiber bundle)

- Shift one surface and its opposite surface by 0.1 mm in opposite directions.
- Apply $\hat{u}_2 = 0.1 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{7.2} y_1\right)$ during that interval.

□ Conditions

- Carried out by Abaqus Standard 2018.
- Elastic analysis.

y_1, y_2 tensile, $y_1 y_2$ shear
 y_1, y_2 bending, $y_1 y_2$ torsion

Parameters of fiber bundle	
$E_L = 143.9$ GPa	$E_T = 8.88$ GPa
$\nu_{LT} = 0.304$	$\nu_{TT} = 0.452$
$G_{LT} = 4.52$ GPa	$G_{TT} = 3.4$ GPa

Parameters of resin	
$E = 3.1042$ GPa	$\nu = 0.438$

Reference model

1. Prepare two sinusoidal waviness models.
2. Tilt RUC to impose the conventional periodic boundary conditions.

A model in which one surface and its opposite surface are matched, with only the interior being undulated.

□ Point to note

- Because the phase is shifted by half a period, the stress distribution is inverted.

Nodes: 41,555, Elements: 88,576

Fiber bundles: tetra element (C3D4), Resin: tetra element (C3D4)

y_1 7.2 mm \times y_2 3.6 mm \times y_3 1.1 mm

□ Conditions

- Same for the proposed method.

Concept of reference model.

One surface and its opposite surface.

Stress distribution

y_1 tensile
Stress σ_{11} [MPa]

y_2
 y_1

The effect of microscopic defects is significant.

Proposed method

Model for validation

Fiber bundle	Proposed method	Reference model
Minimum stress [MPa]	1321	1320
Maximum stress [MPa]	1555	1569

- The stress distributions generally match.
- The difference between two models is approximately 0.90%.

Demonstrate the validity of the proposed method in **microscopic** properties.

Stiffness matrix

Proposed method

$$\begin{bmatrix} 112318 & 2654 & 949 & & & \\ 2654 & 7730 & 11 & & & \\ 949 & 11 & 2981 & & & \\ & & & 8850 & 242 & 13 \\ & 0 & & 241 & 720 & -2 \\ & & & 13 & -2 & 324 \end{bmatrix}$$

Reference model

$$\begin{bmatrix} 112921 & 2605 & 2908 & & & \\ 2605 & 7422 & 26 & & & \\ 2908 & 26 & 2951 & & & \\ & & & 8796 & 226 & 221 \\ & 0 & & 226 & 675 & 5 \\ & & & 221 & 5 & 314 \end{bmatrix}$$

- Compared to the large-scale component (1,1), components that are three orders of magnitude smaller are significantly affected by numerical errors.
- Excluding these components, the two are in good agreement.

Demonstrate the validity of the proposed method in **macroscopic** properties

Stiffness matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix}$$

[A] : In-plane stiffness [MPa mm]
 [B] : Coupling stiffness [MPa mm²]
 [D] : Bending stiffness [MPa mm³]

Defects model (woven composite **with** microscopic defects)

Nodes: 109,784, Elements: 446,661
Fiber bundles : tetra element (C3D4), Resin : hexa element (C3D8)
 y_1 7.98 mm \times y_2 4.18 mm \times y_3 3.062 mm

- The preprocessing time is approximately **2 hours**.*
- Implemented by the proposed method.

Ideal model (woven composite **without** microscopic defects)

Nodes: 172,607, Elements: 343,956
Fiber bundles : hexa element (C3D8), Resin : tetra element (C3D4)
 y_1 8.56 mm \times y_2 4.26 mm \times y_3 3.12 mm

- It takes about **1 month** to outsource mesh generation to a specialized contractor.
- Implemented by the conventional method.

binder

weft

warp

resin

Ideal model

Stress distribution ($E_{11} = 0.01$)

y_1 tensile

Stress σ_{11} [MPa]

2200

-30

Defects model

Ideal model

The microscopic defects are small, so the trends in the stress distribution are similar but not identical.
For **microscopic** properties, the influence of microscopic defects is significant.

Stiffness matrix

Defects model

105585	8815	176	-1835	-53	-104
8815	275697	-198	-52	-1200	205
176	-198	11461	-85	-260	-171
-1835	-52	-85	23913	6573	81
-53	-1200	-260	6573	225597	-98
-104	205	-171	81	-98	8133

Ideal model

105933	8134	1	-1	0	0
8163	260168	1	0	5	0
1	1	10614	0	0	0
-2	0	0	21193	6199	1
0	5	0	6254	216739	0
0	0	0	1	0	7488

- The coupling stiffness of defects model is not zero.
 - Defects model is not symmetric due to the microscopic defects.
- In terms of in-plane stiffness and bending stiffness, the difference between two models is small.
 - For macroscopic properties such as tensile behavior, the influence of microscopic defects is small.
 - The influence of microscopic defects is averaged.

Conclusion

A multiscale analysis method for RUC with incomplete periodicity due to microscopic defects has been proposed.

- By deriving the actual macroscopic strain from the macroscopic strain applied to the nominal model, a brief formulation of the proposed method was given.
- The mesh-separated analysis method was introduced to simplify meshing resin elements.
- Using a simple model with a single fiber bundle embedded in resin, the validity of the proposed method was demonstrated.
- The proposed method was applied to a woven composite model.
⇒ Microscopic defects have a significant impact on microscopic properties, whereas their effect on macroscopic properties is marginal.

Appendix

Tolerance range for microscopic defects

Microscopic displacement at point P^1 in the actual model :

$$u_i(y_i^1) = \tilde{E}_{ij}y_j + \tilde{K}_{ij}y_jy_3 + u_i^1(y_i) \cdots (2)$$

By taking the volume average of Eq.(2), macroscopic strain for actual model is gained.

In the calculation, **the squared term** of the microscopic defects is approximated as **negligible** to simplify the formulation.

- The proposed method is applicable in the range where the above holds.
- This approximation leads to errors in the stiffness matrix

Macroscopic strain at point P^1 :

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{E}_{ij}^{real} &= \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_{Y^1} \varepsilon_{ij} dY^1 = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \varepsilon_{ij} \det|J| dY \\ &= \tilde{E}_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \tilde{E}_{ik} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \tilde{E}_{jk} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_i} dY \cdots (3) \end{aligned}$$

How to make nominal model

To apply the proposed method, the following two conditions are required.

- ① Periodic boundary condition by Key-DOF method.

Apply to the corresponding nodes on the surface of RUC.

- ② A transformation matrix [X]

Characters appearing in [X]:
$$U_{kj} = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY \dots (12)$$

Integrate Eq.(12) once and convert it into a surface integral.

$$\int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_1} dY = \int_{S_{y_2 y_3}} [\hat{u}_k]_{-\partial y_1}^{\partial y_1} dy_2 dy_3 \dots (26)$$

It is sufficient to define only the surface of RUC.

Actual model

Nominal model

- To make nominal model,
1. Extract only the surface of the actual model.
 2. Average the corresponding surface.

Transformation matrix [X]

Characters appearing in [X]:

$$U_{kj} = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY \dots (12)$$

$$U_{kj}^3 = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y y_3 \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY \dots (13)$$

$$U_{kj}^{-3} = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \frac{1}{y_3} \frac{\partial \hat{u}_k}{\partial y_j} dY \dots (14)$$

$$y^3 = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y y_3 \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1}{\partial y_1} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2}{\partial y_2} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_3}{\partial y_3} \right) dY \dots (15)$$

$$y^{-3} = \frac{1}{|Y^1|} \int_Y \frac{1}{y_3} \left(\frac{\partial \hat{u}_1}{\partial y_1} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_2}{\partial y_2} + \frac{\partial \hat{u}_3}{\partial y_3} \right) dY \dots (16)$$

Macroscopic strain and curvature for the actual model :

$$\tilde{E}_{ij}^{real} = \tilde{E}_{ij} + y^3 \tilde{K}_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{ik} U_{kj} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{jk} U_{ki} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{ik} U_{kj}^3 - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{jk} U_{ki}^3 \dots (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{K}_{ij}^{real} = & \tilde{K}_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{ik} U_{kj}^{-3} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{jk} U_{ki}^{-3} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{ik} U_{kj} - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{jk} U_{ki} \\ & - \tilde{K}_{ij} y^{-3} y^3 + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{ik} y^{-3} U_{kj} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{E}_{jk} y^{-3} U_{ki} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{ik} y^{-3} U_{kj}^3 + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{K}_{jk} y^{-3} U_{ki}^3 \dots (18) \end{aligned}$$

Transformation matrix [X]

The macroscopic strain at point P^1 can be written by applying a transformation matrix [X] to the macroscopic strain enforced at point P :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{real} = [X] \tilde{\mathbf{E}} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

This transformation matrix [X] associate actual model with nominal model.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{E}_{11}^{real} \\ \tilde{E}_{22}^{real} \\ 2\tilde{E}_{12}^{real} \\ \tilde{K}_{11}^{real} \\ \tilde{K}_{22}^{real} \\ 2\tilde{K}_{12}^{real} \end{Bmatrix} = [X] \begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{E}_{11} \\ \tilde{E}_{22} \\ 2\tilde{E}_{12} \\ \tilde{K}_{11} \\ \tilde{K}_{22} \\ 2\tilde{K}_{12} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$[X] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - U_{11} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2}U_{21} & y^3 - U_{11}^3 & 0 & -\frac{1}{2}U_{21}^3 \\ 0 & 1 - U_{22} & -\frac{1}{2}U_{12} & 0 & y^3 - U_{22}^3 & -\frac{1}{2}U_{12}^3 \\ -U_{12} & -U_{21} & 1 - \frac{1}{2}U_{22} - \frac{1}{2}U_{11} & -U_{12}^3 & -U_{21}^3 & y^3 - \frac{1}{2}U_{22}^3 - \frac{1}{2}U_{11}^3 \\ y^{-3}U_{11} - U_{11}^{-3} & 0 & y^{-3}U_{21} - U_{21}^{-3} & 1 - y^{-3}y^3 + y^{-3}U_{11}^3 - U_{11} & 0 & \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{21}^3 - U_{21}) \\ 0 & y^{-3}U_{22} - U_{22}^{-3} & y^{-3}U_{12} - U_{12}^{-3} & 0 & 1 - y^{-3}y^3 + y^{-3}U_{22}^3 - U_{22} & \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{12}^3 - U_{12}) \\ \frac{1}{2}y^{-3}U_{12} - \frac{1}{2}U_{12}^{-3} & \frac{1}{2}y^{-3}U_{21} - \frac{1}{2}U_{21}^{-3} & \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{22} - U_{22}^{-3}) + \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{11} - U_{11}^{-3}) & y^{-3}U_{12}^3 - U_{12} & y^{-3}U_{21}^3 - U_{21} & 1 - y^{-3}y^3 + \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{22}^3 - U_{22}) + \frac{1}{2}(y^{-3}U_{11}^3 - U_{11}) \end{bmatrix}$$

Key-DOF method^[1]

- ① Add imaginary nodes (with six degrees of freedom) at an arbitrary location.

Displacement of imaginary node 1 : $(d_1^{key}, d_2^{key}, d_3^{key})$

Displacement of imaginary node 2 : $(d_4^{key}, d_5^{key}, d_6^{key})$

- ② Enforce macroscopic strain to the key degree of freedom.

$$d_1^{key} = E_{11}, d_2^{key} = E_{22}, d_3^{key} = 2E_{12}$$

$$d_4^{key} = K_{11}, d_5^{key} = K_{22}, d_6^{key} = 2K_{12}$$

Method for calculating resultant force and moment

- From the relationship between the work applied through the key degrees of freedom and strain energy stored inside RUC, the following equation is derived.

$$f_1^{key} = |S|N_{11}, f_2^{key} = |S|N_{22}, f_3^{key} = |S|N_{12} \quad f_4^{key} = |S|M_{11}, f_5^{key} = |S|M_{22}, f_6^{key} = |S|M_{12}$$

[1]: S. Li, N. Warror, Z. Zou, F. Almaskari: A unit cell for FE analysis of materials with the microstructure of a staggered pattern, Composites: Part A, Vol. 42 (2011), pp. 801-811.

Key-DOF method^[1]

The stress-strain relationship:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_{11}^1 & N_{11}^2 & N_{11}^3 & N_{11}^4 & N_{11}^5 & N_{11}^6 \\ N_{22}^1 & N_{22}^2 & N_{22}^3 & N_{22}^4 & N_{22}^5 & N_{22}^6 \\ N_{12}^1 & N_{12}^2 & N_{12}^3 & N_{12}^4 & N_{12}^5 & N_{12}^6 \\ M_{11}^1 & M_{11}^2 & M_{11}^3 & M_{11}^4 & M_{11}^5 & M_{11}^6 \\ M_{22}^1 & M_{22}^2 & M_{22}^3 & M_{22}^4 & M_{22}^5 & M_{22}^6 \\ M_{12}^1 & M_{12}^2 & M_{12}^3 & M_{12}^4 & M_{12}^5 & M_{12}^6 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}}_{[C_{key}]} \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & E_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

② Resultant force obtained by the result of the analysis.

$[C_{key}]$
Stiffness matrix calculated by the Key-DOF method

① Enforce 6 types of macroscopic strain

[1]:S.Li, N.Warrior, Z.Zou, F.Almaskari: A unit cell for FE analysis of materials with the microstructure of a staggered pattern, Composites: Part A, Vol. 42 (2011), pp. 801-811.

□ Periodic boundary condition

$$\begin{aligned}u_1(a, y_2, y_3) - u_1(-a, y_2, y_3) &= 2aE_{11} + 2ay_3K_{11} \\u_2(a, y_2, y_3) - u_2(-a, y_2, y_3) &= 2aE_{12} + 2ay_3K_{12} \\u_3(a, y_2, y_3) - u_3(-a, y_2, y_3) &= -2ay_2K_{12}\end{aligned}$$

In Abaqus, there is an option called “*equation” that allows you to apply multipoint constraints in the form of linear equations.

*EQUATION

(The number of terms in the linear equation)

(Node ID of one surface), (Degree of freedom to be constrained), (Coefficients of the linear equation), · · ·

The interface stiffness

In Abaqus, there is an option that allows you to cohesive zone model(CZM).

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| *SURFACE | ⇒ Define two surfaces for applying CZM. |
| *CONTACT PAIR | ⇒ Define the pair of surfaces that make up the interface. |
| *Surface Interaction | } Define how the surfaces are connected to each other. |
| *Cohesive Behavior | |
| *Damage Initiation | |
| *Damage Evolution | |

In the proposed method,

1. Place several reference points for applying CZM to the surface of the fiber bundle elements.
 2. Find the cut element that the reference point belongs to.
 3. Interpolate the reference point from the nodes of the cut element, using shape function.
 4. Define CZM between the two **reference points**.
- ※ The formula for CZM is the same.

Element type

In the proposed method,

Fiber bundles : tetra element (C3D4), Resin : hexa element (C3D8)

- Because microscopic defects make the shape of the fiber bundles complex, it is not always possible to mesh it with hexa elements.
- Because mesh-separated analysis method is used, the resin can be easily meshed. So, more accurate hexa elements are employed.

In the conventional method,

Fiber bundles : hexa element (C3D8), Resin : tetra element (C3D4)

- Because the fiber bundles are idealized by ignoring the effects of microscopic defects, the fiber bundles can be meshed with hexa elements.
- To generate meshes so that the resin conforms along the interfaces of the fiber bundles, it is not always possible to mesh it with hexa elements.

Preprocessing for the proposed method.

1. Our collaborative research partner make the fiber bundles model from the X-ray CT results.
(They said it won't take much time since it's just the fiber bundles.)
2. Make a nominal model of fiber bundles from an actual fiber bundles model.
3. Construct the resin at its nominal position so that it forms a regular block mesh.
(This makes it easier to impose periodic boundary conditions.)
4. Make an actual resin model from a nominal resin model.
5. Remove cut elements overlapped by fiber bundles.
6. Find reference points for applying cohesive zone model(CZM).

Woven composite

Weft bundles

Resin

Binder

Warp bundles

Ideal model

Woven composite

Weft bundles

Resin

Binder

Warp bundles

- The methods for creating models differ between defects models and ideal models.
- The dimensions of the models are different.
- The fiber bundle volume fraction differs by 0.36%.
- Even though the influence of microscopic defects is averaged, the macroscopic properties do not match exactly, but they show similar values.

	Defects model	Ideal model
Length in the y_1 -axis direction [mm]	7.98	8.56
Length in the y_2 -axis direction [mm]	4.18	4.26
Length in the y_3 -axis direction [mm]	3.13	3.12
Volume of the fiber bundle [mm ³]	62.0	67.4
Volume of RUC [mm ³]	104	114
Fiber bundle volume fraction [%]	59.4	59.2

Ideal model

The resin elements sandwiched between the fiber bundles are extremely thin.

- Very difficult to create such elements.
- In finite element analysis, elements get distorted, which leads to deterioration of convergence.

The resin elements sandwiched between the fiber bundles are extremely thin.

- Very difficult to generate a conforming resin mesh.

Because of the above reasons,
making the idealized model is time-consuming.

Floating elements in proposed method

- When removing void elements in preprocessing, we need to determine whether the resin elements are overlapped by the fiber bundles, but handling the error tolerances is a pain.
- Even if resin elements remain isolated, they won't affect the analysis because they aren't connected to any other elements.

How to remove void elements

1. Place several reference points in resin element.
2. If the dot product of the normal vector of each surface of the fiber bundle element and the position vector of the reference point is zero or negative, the reference point is judged to be inside the fiber bundle.
3. If the number of reference points judged to be inside equals the total number of placed reference points, the resin element is a void element.

